

CAUSES OF UNEMPLOYMENT IN INDIA: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract:

Population and employment growth in every nation are critical for economic success. Unemployment is a big issue for many emerging economies, including India. In a time of high unemployment, individuals are eager to find a job that meets their needs and qualifications, but many are unable to find one. There is less and less employment available in India, yet the country's young population continues to rise. In this case, there is an imbalance between demand and supply, resulting in a high unemployment rate. There is a great deal of risk and unpredictability in the agricultural and industrial sectors. As a result of the public's disinterest in agriculture and industry, a high level of unemployment has risen. The same work attracts many individuals, while others are uninterested in any career. In times of economic hardship, those who are jobless confront a wide range of issues, including physical and psychological harassment, despair and social abuse and being pressured to turn to criminal activity or violence as a means of earning a living. This study investigates the origins and possible solutions to unemployment in India.

Key Words: Unemployment, Causes, Remedies

Introduction:

Unemployment in India is examined in light of the present conditions. Unemployment is a big concern in all emerging countries, including India. India has a burgeoning young population despite a tight labour market. Unemployment and the pace at which it is created are both at a highly rapid compound rate due to a lack of supply in this situation. Agriculture and industry face a significant degree of risk and unpredictability. India's rising rate of unemployment is unquestionably a severe issue. No matter how hard we try, we will never be able to achieve success in anything, and this is especially true as the world's population grows. We must address the issue of unemployment in such a way that everyone may find work that they like and that contributes to the country's overall progress. The Center for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE) estimates that 53 million individuals would be jobless in December 2021, with a majority of them being women. A total of 35 million of them are actively looking for employment, while another 17 million are eager to work but not searching seriously. As of December 2021, 35 million people were unemployed in India, 7.9 percent of the population, and they were actively looking for work."

The surge in Covid-19 cases after the appearance of the Omicron version throughout the globe has been blamed for the drop-in economic activity and consumer confidence, both of which have contributed to the increase in the number of unemployed. Meanwhile, a recent survey found that urban Indians are more concerned about unemployment and coronavirus. According to the results of the Ipsos what Worries the World global poll for December, 70% of urban Indians likewise feel that the nation is headed in the right way. Indians, on the other hand, are alarmed by the high rate of unemployment and the uncertainty surrounding their work prospects. Around 18 per cent of the world's total population lives in India, which has a population of 1.3 billion. When it comes to joblessness, India and the rest of the world aren't alone. To lessen the risk of unemployment in India, it is essential to study and understand the issue. Unemployment and economic growth are two of the most pressing issues facing every country's economy as it grows. India's most pressing issue is the high rate of unemployment. It's getting worse by the minute. Unemployed people are actively looking for work but are unable to find it. Lack of practical skills and uneven industrialization all contribute to higher unemployment rates. Poverty, stress, criminality, and other forms of social and economic inequality have all risen as a result—people who are looking for work but cannot find any. The percentage of the workforce that is unemployed is known as unemployment. The number of persons out of work fluctuates depending on the economy and other factors. As a nation's economic and social structure are impacted by unemployment, it is a multifaceted challenge.

Definition of Unemployment:

Prof. Pigou defines it as, "A man is unemployed only when he is without a job or not employed and also desires to be employed." According to Rafin and Gregori, "An unemployed person that person who is not currently employed is actively looking for work, is currently available for work at the existing wage rate."

Indian Unemployment: What It Means:

Irrespective of the economy or development stage, all countries throughout the globe are confronted with the problem of high rates of unemployment. However, unemployment in less developed or emerging countries is vastly different from that seen in more affluent nations. As a result of rapid population increase and

moderate economic expansion, affluent nations like the United States are grappling with involuntary and frictional unemployment, whilst emerging countries like India are dealing with structural unemployment.

Both visible and covert forms of structural unemployment exist. But the most dangerous kind of unemployment in developing nations like India is the widespread underemployment or hidden unemployment in the rural sector. As a society, we have an unemployment issue. In this case, the total number of job openings is much fewer than the entire number of job searchers in the nation. Despite their desire and ability to work, jobless people cannot get meaningful or financially rewarding positions. In this way, joblessness results in a massive loss of personnel resources. India's unemployment issue stems from a lack of capital equipment and other complementary resources, compounded by the country's rapidly increasing population. The following table shows the unemployment percentage in India and states.

Table 1

S.No	State	In the month of December 2021 Unemployment Percentage
1	Andhra Pradesh	5.6
2	Assam	5.8
3	Bihar	16
4	Chhattisgarh	2.1
5	Delhi	9.8
6	Goa	12
7	Gujarat	1.6
8	Haryana	34.1
9	Himachal Pradesh	9.4
10	Jammu & Kashmir	15
11	Jharkhand	17.3
12	Karnataka	1.4
13	Kerala	6.7
14	Madhya Pradesh	3.4
15	Maharashtra	3.8
16	Meghalaya	3
17	Odisha	1.6
18	Puducherry	6.2
19	Punjab	6.8
20	Rajasthan	27.1
21	Sikkim	NA
22	Tamil Nadu	6.9
23	Telangana	2.2
24	Tripura	14.7
25	Uttar Pradesh	4.9
26	Uttarakhand	5
27	West Bengal	7.3
28	India	7.9

Source: The Unemployment Rates are produced by CMIE using its Consumer Pyramids Household Survey machinery. Production of these unemployment rates and their public distribution is sponsored by CMIE. https://unemploymentinindia.cmie.com/kommon/bin/sr.php?kall=wsttimeseries&index_code=050050000000&dtype=total

Literature Review:

Youth unemployment is a significant concern in Das Sourav (2018)'s research. Another issue that directly affects unemployment is the rapid growth of the population. It's both a financial and societal issue. Kumar Ashwani (2016) also looked at unemployment as a factor in his research. According to the study's findings, employment is closely linked to peace and prosperity. The possibility exists that a jobless young person might go in the wrong route if they do not find work. Consequently, the government should be concerned about this critical issue. Gomathi V and Neela M (2016) discovered in their research that a nation's future success depends on its educated young. On the backs of educated young men and women rests the weight of creating India a perfect socialist state, a duty they should treat with extreme caution.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the causes of unemployment.
- To suggest suitable remedies for the eradication of unemployment.

Methodology:

An exploratory research approach is adopted in this study. In addition to books, journals, and online resources, secondary sources were used to gather data for this study.

Unemployment is Caused by the Following Factors:

The Caste System:

The caste system is widespread throughout India. Certain castes are barred from working in certain places. On many occasions, the task is provided to the individual who belongs to a particular group rather than the suitable applicants. As a result, more people will be out of work.

Slow Slowing Economic Growth:

There is a lot of room for improvement in the Indian economy, yet economic development is modest. There aren't enough job prospects for the growing population due to this country's weak economic growth.

A Rise in the Population:

India's population continues to rise daily. India has a vast and growing young labour force. As far as I know, this phenomenon is widespread around the globe, but in India, the vast majority of the population (about 68.8%) lives in rural regions. Moreover, roughly 70% of our kids come from rural areas in our broken education system. Everyone is aware that the absence of skills and English language proficiency in rural regions is significant in young people's lack of work opportunities. In most cases, people have no idea how to curb population growth. By way of population, it is influenced.

Underdevelopment:

Even though India's natural resources are enormous, the country's economy is still in the nascent stages of development. Economic activity is relatively minimal in scope and magnitude. Non-agricultural industries, in particular the modern industrial sector, which can provide a large number of jobs, are expanding at a glacial pace.

Even before independence, the Indian economy grew slowly. Instead of developing the local small and cottage businesses, the British systematically wiped them off. Even in the post-independence era, the industrial sector's performance has fallen well short of its goals and demands.

In addition, the poor pace of capital creation is a significant factor in stifling economic potential in the agriculture, manufacturing, and infrastructure sector. Consequently, the lack of job growth might be attributed to this underdevelopment.

Lack of Employment Planning:

There has been nothing done to use the rural labour surplus in India's initial phase of economic planning to increase job prospects. Another fundamental flaw in Indian planning is the inability to prepare for human resources adequately. It has resulted in enormous imbalances in educated and skilled professionals, such as engineers, technicians, cost accountants, ordinary graduates, post graduates, administrators, and so forth. Due to a lack of proper workforce planning, many resources were wasted on the development of personnel.

Agriculture's Slowness:

A large part of the country's rural unemployment and underemployment may be attributed to the high population density on the country's land and the rudimentary techniques of agricultural products used to support it. The underdevelopment of agriculture creates unemployment in the country at a high level.

Lack of Industrialization:

The country's industrial development is woefully inadequate. On the contrary, the potential for industrial growth has never been fully realized. Capital, technology, and raw materials were lacking in the country's manufacturing sector; this meant that it couldn't get off the ground and provide adequate jobs for its population.

Lack of Sufficient Education System:

Indian education is riddled with flaws since there is no facility for providing technical and practical training. More and more students are graduating each year, resulting in a widening disparity between the number of jobs available and the number of people looking for work. Many educated young people are frustrated and dissatisfied because they lack access to opportunities for self-employment due to a lack of vocational training and professional assistance.

Joint Family System:

Significant families with big businesses will have many people who don't work but rely on the family's combined revenue for their survival. While many seem to be in action, they have no discernible impact on output. The result is a rise in "disguised unemployment."

Cottage and Small Business Collapse:

Small and cottage enterprises were negatively impacted by industrialization. Many employees lost their jobs due to a decrease in cottage industry output.

Insufficient Irrigation:

Water scarcity limits the yield of many acres of land to a single crop per year. Due to this reason, Farmers spend the majority of the year without a job.

Immobility of Labour:

In India, the movement of labour is quite limited. People are reluctant to relocate far from home because of their connection to their families. Low mobility is also caused by language, religion, and climate factors. Unemployment is exacerbated by the inability of workers to move. All of the above factors exacerbate unemployment.

Remedies for Removal of Unemployment:

In India, every choice should be suitable for decreasing unemployment. The numerous policies should not only be on paper; they should reflect outcomes. India's growing unemployment crisis is unquestionably significant. The answer might be discovered by putting in some effort on the part of the Indian government as well as responsible citizens.

- Government authorities should guarantee the quality of education being given by institutions. It may not be feasible until adequate and frequent surveillance on institutions.
- Every individual must follow excellent government policies, notably for family planning and control of the population.
- The government needs to create large job opportunities for everyone. The huge industries in India should be done to improve the nation.
- Modernizing the agriculture industry throughout the nation is essential if rural unemployment is eradicated.
- To combat rural unemployment, the related sector, which includes activities such as dairying, poultry and beekeeping and fishing, as well as horticulture, sericulture and agro-processing, has to be further developed.
- To combat rural unemployment, the government should use a combination of labour- and capital-intensive production methods to increase employment while also improving productivity in new production areas.
- The central and state governments must work together to establish and execute rural development programmes that will promptly reach the intended demographics to eliminate rural unemployment.
- Based on the local endowment position, it is vital to spread out the placement of industries around small towns to limit the movement of people from rural to urban regions and minimize rural unemployment.
- To provide self-employment prospects, adequate measures must be made to promote self-help groups (SHGs). As a result, the micro-finance flow from NGOs to SHGs may play a significant role in addressing rural unemployment.
- Immediate actions to improve industrial efficiency must be implemented to address the issue of urban unemployment.
- The government should develop realistic urban employment creation plans like PMRY, NRY, etc., to help the jobless in urban areas launch their self-employment ventures.
- Unemployment may be reduced significantly by appropriately and scientifically managing human resources.

Conclusion:

India's primary concern is unemployment. Labour opportunities are scarce among the population. Because of the unemployment, the nation is not developing. As a result of this, only a few individuals can find work, while most of the population stays jobless. As a result, India has a significant unemployment issue. Institutions find it more challenging to develop needed skills to the level necessary to get a job in any excellent sector. The lack of employment, GDP, and inflation problems in India's economy directly impacts the quality of life for the standard population. It is thus recommended that Indian authorities focus on reorganizing the Indian economy, rising employment rates, and managing price volatility. A number of the recommendations made in this study should be taken under consideration by the Indian government. Instead of importing foreign ideas, the Indian government should put more effort into developing the country's resources. For Research & development money should be provided by the Indian government so that India may develop cutting-edge technology that would create more jobs while also providing workers with a decent wage.

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